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Natural Neon-Helium Mixture as Working Fluid for 40-80 K Cryogenic Refrigerators

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ABSTRACT

A general quest in the design of cryogenic systems is to ensure high efficiency and low cost. Cryogenic refrigerators for HTS cables require 10-25 kW cooling capacity at a temperature below 77 K. The reversed Brayton cycle is recognized as the most promising process for this application. Prototype systems based mainly on neon as a refrigerant and oil-free turbo-compressors with magnetic bearings have been developed by some suppliers in the last decade. Unfortunately, there are no reports available about their operation and corresponding maintenance cost. However, the relatively high cost of pure neon as refrigerant can affect the economics of this application. An alternative working fluid for such systems, earlier proposed by the TU Dresden is Nelium – a mixture of neon and helium. In the context of the mixture composition optimisation, the neon production process was studied and is described in this paper. The “Natural Nelium” – a mixture containing helium, neon and hydrogen with a composition according to the relative proportion of these gases in air (patent is pending) – was found to be attractive as a potential refrigerant. The power demand, process parameters at each production stage and process design are discussed in the paper.

Keywords: Neon-Helium mixture, Nelium, Neon production, Brayton cycle.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cryogenic refrigerators for temperatures lower than the liquid nitrogen level are required for cooling of superconducting devices. For the 40-80 K temperature range only neon, helium, hydrogen and their mixtures can be used as refrigerants thanks to their low triple and critical points. Hydrogen could be a preferred refrigerant because of the lowest cost (Fig. 1), but the molar mass of hydrogen is extremely low, a compression of hydrogen in a turbo-compressor is practically not possible. Moreover, hydrogen is flammable, therefore only pure neon and pure helium were considered as working fluids in the past.

Figure 1: Relative market prices of gases (purity grade 5.0) compared to the price of hydrogen per Nm³ (cubic meter at 0 °C, 1013.25 mbar), average of quotation from industry

Generally, the reversed Brayton process is considered as the most promising option for required cooling purposes. The conventional systems use pure helium as refrigerant and oil-injected screw compressors, which is a sort of standard technology in helium refrigeration. However, the relatively low isothermal efficiency of

these compressors (50-60 %) results in a low (20-30 %) overall cycle efficiency. The second type of systems are refrigerators based on oil-free turbo-compressors. This kind of systems has been developed by three suppliers: Mayekawa (5 kW at 69 K), Air Liquide (from 7.8 to 152.4 kW at 25-200 K) and Taiyo Nippon Sanso (2 and 10 kW at 69 K). It uses turbo-compressors with magnetic bearings and mainly neon as refrigerant. The process efficiency of some systems may reach 41 % at 77 K (Nakamura, N., 2017; Gondrand, C., 2014; Hirai, H., et al., 2014; Yoshida, S., et al., 2014), which is a high value. Unfortunately, detailed information about performance of these refrigerators and operation cost is not available. Nevertheless, the price of neon, which is up to 7-10 times higher compared to helium (Fig. 1), may cause a high maintenance cost and may become a limiting factor for the wide application of such a system.

The application of a neon-helium mixture, the so-called Nelium, and the design of the corresponding Turbo-Brayton cycle was earlier proposed by TU Dresden (Quack, H. et al., 2015; Klöppel, S. et al., 2015). It combines advantages of the previously named systems and allows to reach an overall process efficiency of 45 % at 40 K. Generally, the concentration of neon and helium in this mixture is a free optimization parameter and has to be chosen according to the target function of optimization (cost or power or combination of both).

The conventional method of Nelium production is the mixing of pure and therefore expensive neon and helium, which leads to high costs of this refrigerant. However, as within the neon production process neon is extracted from the neon-helium mixture produced from air, it could be economically reasonable to use this pre-product mixture directly as a refrigerant. In such a way some expensive separation sequences can be avoided. The considered neon-helium mixture, the so-called Natural Nelium, has the composition according to the ratio of these gases in air: 74.6 % neon, 25.4 % helium. The Natural Nelium can additionally contain hydrogen depending on the point of its extraction from the pure neon production process and the Brayton system requirements. To determine the possibilities of this Natural Nelium use, the neon production process was studied and is described in this paper.

2. NEON PRODUCTION PROCESS STUDY

Neon is a product of the air separation industry. It is an inert gas with a natural content in the air of 18 ppm only, so special systems are required to extract and separate it from the other air components. The process of neon production with some variations is well-described in literature (Kerry, F.G., 2007; Hausen, H., Linde, H., 1985; Häring, H.-W., 2008; Bondarenko, V.L., Simonenko Yu. M., 2014). It is used in industry since more than 100 years. The process was simulated in the present work using the PRO II process simulator and the Soave Redlich-Kwong equation of state. The data are summarized and typical process steps are subsequently described in the current paper.

2.1. Stage 1 – Extraction from the air

The main source of neon is the so-called vent gas, which is obtained from the top of the high-pressure column of the air separation plant (Fig. 2, stream 1). Its composition can slightly vary depending on the column parameters, but generally, it contains approximately 97.4 % nitrogen, 0.6 % helium, 1.8 % neon, 0.2 % hydrogen and some ppm of other atmospheric gases. Neon, helium and hydrogen, being non-condensable at the operation temperature, accumulate in the condenser of the column and reduce the partial pressure of nitrogen. This gas has to be removed from the column for stable operation of this unit (Fig. 2). Generally, this vent gas can be considered as a more or less cost-free raw material for the neon production.

2.2. Stage 2 – Crude Neon-Helium production

The first step of the conventional neon enrichment process is a partial removal of nitrogen. Usually this is done directly at the air separation plant site, where the pre-enrichment column is installed (Fig. 2, SC). This column operates at around 5.5 bar and consists of a couple of trays and a condenser at the top for generation of liquid reflux. According to the enthalpy balance a small additional cooling capacity is required to drive this process. For a process design with 100 mol/s feed-gas approx. 10 kW are needed (2 % of the total cooling power) and can be covered by supplementary liquid nitrogen supply (stream LN₂). The resulting product gas (stream 2,

The vapour from the top of the column consists of nearly 50 % of the neon. This stream is recycled by means of a recycle-compressor.

Product in liquid state is obtained in this system (1.72 mol/s for 100 mol/s of crude gas). If the pure neon is required in gas phase, additional 12 kW cooling power could be extracted from the product flow (stream 8) by passing it through the pre-cooling heat exchangers. Thus, the cooling power of the refrigerator can be reduced from 4.2 kW to 0.2 kW. Cooling from 26 to 29 K will be needed. That results in a reduction of the required input power from 147 kW in the initial case down to 14 kW. However, additional 28 kW power will be needed to compress the neon gas product from 1.7 bar to 200 bar for further storage and transportation. The conventional technical solution is for a liquid product stream and thus requires the 147 kW refrigerator.

Figure 3: Removal of helium: C – compressor; HX1, HX2, HX3 – heat exchangers; M – mixer; R – refrigerator; RC – rectification column; S - separator

2.4. Expenses of the neon production process

Table 1. Energy consumption and purity levels of neon production stages for the inlet crude gas flow of 100 mol/s

Stages		1	2			3			
		Extraction	N ₂ separation	Compression to 200 bar	H ₂ removal	Final N ₂ removal	Compression to 29 bar	Precooling to 70 K	Cooling to 26 K
W, kW		0	~10	40	-	17	9	9	147
p, bar		5.5	5.5	200.0	1.0	1.0	29.6	29.5	29.2
T, K		95	300	300	600-700	77	300	70	26
V, mol/s		100		3.49	3.29	2.36		1.72	
Composition, mole %	Ne	1.8	50.5		53.5	74.6		99.99-99.999	
	He	0.6	17.2		18.2	25.4		1-5 ppm	
	H ₂	0.2	5.7		-	-		-	
	N ₂	97.4	26.7		28.2	-		-	

The enthalpies of recycled cold streams were included in the calculations. Consequently, the total energy consumption results in 232 kW for 1.72 mol/s of the liquid product, which is equal to 1.57 kWh for 1 Nm³ of

neon. This number means, that the power cost is very low compared to the market price of the gas. Consequently, the high cost of neon should be explained by other reasons only, as may be supposed, by high capital expenses for refrigeration and separation equipment and instrumentation. The targeted refrigerant cost reduction can be achieved by avoiding of some process steps. Herewith some preliminary considerations about this issue: 1) the nitrogen removal in crude helium-neon production unit is based on a separation column. However, this rectification unit is not very sophisticated, because the liquefaction temperature of nitrogen is much higher than the one of neon, helium and hydrogen and the targeted product purity is relatively low; 2) in contrast, the hydrogen removal unit requires a complicated oxidation system and expensive catalysts; 3) the helium removal unit requires a cryogenic refrigerator for cooling at 26 K and an additional rectification column for the polishing. An expensive instrumentation system, especially gas analysis, is necessary for the final purification stage, as well. This very simple analysis indicates that the hydrogen removal and helium removal process steps have the highest impact on the neon product cost.

3. CONSIDERATION CONCERNING OPTIMAL NELIUM COMPOSITION

The main idea of making Natural Nelium economically more advantageous than the pure neon is to reduce the cost for the final purification by avoiding of two steps: hydrogen removal as well as helium removal. According to the neon production process analysis, the hydrogen separation stage would require high capital expenses compared to the crude Nelium production. Thus, it would be economically reasonable to avoid this stage for the Natural Nelium. As the requirements for the refrigerant in a 40-80 K temperature range are not so strict regarding the hydrogen content, it seems to be a feasible option. The final Nelium mixture containing 68.8 % of neon, 23.4 % of helium and 7.8 % of hydrogen is recognized as a most attractive option in terms of production cost. It is expected, that the avoiding of the last two stages of neon production would make the price of the Natural Nelium significantly lower than pure neon price and comparable with the price of helium.

Consequently, the raw materials for the Nelium production can be purchased from the supplier in two forms: as a vent gas directly from the air separation unit (after stage 1) or as a crude neon-helium mixture after stage 2. Both options require a compression unit (200 bar) and a corresponding number of gas cylinders for storage and transport purposes. That means additional equipment and energy. For vent gas (stream 1) the estimated ideal work of full nitrogen separation is 30 kW for 100 mol/s of the inlet mixture, which corresponds to 0.2 kWh per 1 kg of gas. For the crude-neon-helium mixture (stream 2) it is 5 kW for 3.49 mol/s flow (0.04 kWh for 1 kg of the gas). Both options are feasible and depend on the capabilities of the air separation plant.

In a previous study it was found, that the optimal composition of Nelium from the process design perspective should consist of more helium (and less neon), because it helps to reduce the temperature difference at the cold end of the heat exchanger (Klöppel, S. et al, 2015). However, it results in high requirements on the turbo-compressor. The recommended Natural Nelium with hydrogen (with a molar mass of 14.98 g/mol, which is equivalent to a mixture of 68 % neon and 32 % helium) is advantageous in this sense and requires an acceptable pressure ratio for turbo-compressors. The heat transfer properties of hydrogen are better, compared to helium. Therefore, the hydrogen in the Natural Nelium will provide a positive impact on the heat exchanger performance: the thermal conductivity of the Natural Nelium is 30 % higher than of the pure neon.

For the Natural Nelium production the final required purity, e.g. a maximum allowed nitrogen content, has to be known. The theoretical value (to avoid solidification at 40 K) depends on the process design (mainly pressure). A value of 2 ppm fulfils this requirement for the whole pressure range (Fig. 4). In regard to oxygen, after the nitrogen adsorption it will be removed from the mixture, which avoids any hydrogen safety issue.

Figure 4: Maximum tolerable nitrogen impurities depending on the low pressure of the Brayton cycle

4. CONCLUSION

“Natural Nelium” consisting of 68.8 % neon, 23.4 % helium and 7.8 % hydrogen was found to be a promising working fluid for Turbo-Brayton cryogenic cycles in the 40-80 K temperature range. The typical neon production process was studied to determine the potential supply stage for the Nelium. An energetic analysis of the production process is presented. The Natural Nelium properties and its purity were discussed. Further studies concerning the Turbo-Brayton processes and component analysis for the considered mixture are planned.

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NOMENCLATURE

T	temperature (K)	V	molar flow ($\text{mol}\times\text{s}^{-1}$)
p	pressure (bar)	W	energy consumption (kW)

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